

THE METHODOLOGICAL PRINCIPLES OF PREPARING PRIMARY SCHOOL PUPILS FOR THE INTERNATIONAL PIRLS TEST

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Abstract. *The given article discusses the methodological foundations of preparing primary school pupils for the control of the international assessment program PIRLS by developing their skills of logical, analytical, critical, creative and independent thinking.*

Keywords: *literary education, literary analysis and interpretation, didactic rule, deduction, induction, critical, creative, independent thinking, creative abilities.*

It is important to suggest that due to the widespread introduction of innovative pedagogical technologies into the education system in the modern conditions of globalization, the implementation of pupils' creative abilities through the formation of logical, analytical, critical, creative, independent thinking skills is an important aspect of personality-oriented development. Education has a great importance in raising the younger generation to a level that meets the requirements of the world standard. In particular, the Progress in International Reading Literacy Study for monitoring reading literacy in primary grades bears great responsibility for teaching reading while meeting the requirements of PIRLS.

Definitely, PIRLS program, organized by the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IAEEA), aims to determine the level of primary school pupils' proficiency in reading in countries with a developed education system and to highlight notable aspects of the system of countries participating in the study aimed at learning. Although there is a significant difference in the age of pupils in countries involved in monitoring the quality of reading and understanding of text in primary schools according to the world standard (in England, New Zealand, Finland, children are taught from the age of five, in many countries they study from the age of six or seven), the demand is the same for everyone [2; 8].

It is known to everyone that the main goal of monitoring the quality of education according to the requirements of PIRLS or FIMSS, that is, the quality and trends of reading literacy, is to periodically study and control the results obtained at different times on different samples using different educational instruments, to compare and draw appropriate conclusion.

From this point of view, the issue of achieving reading literacy, that is, ensuring pupils' speech competence, such as listening comprehension, reading comprehension, speaking and writing, is relevant in the education system of Uzbekistan.

The fourth year of primary education is an important stage in the development of children. During this period, pupils must learn to study at a level that should ensure their successful acquisition of knowledge and skills at the next stage of education.

Besides that, pupils that complete the fourth grade of primary school in 2021 will be assessed based on the PIRLS program in two different types of learning: during training and extracurricular activities. Due to this, it is designed:

to determine the level of learning in order to acquire the experience of mastering in the literary education system;

to determine the level of learning associated with the assimilation of information given in the educational process and its practical use.

According to the conceptual rules of the study, pupils' ability to read fiction and popular science texts is assessed according to the following 4 criteria:

- identifying the information given in the text; (using the analysis of scientific and popular texts as an example)

- drawing conclusions (literary analysis);

- interpreting and summarizing data (literary analysis);

- analyzing the content of the text, its linguistic features and structure (literary analysis).

It is not a secret that analysis of popular science and fiction works enables pupils to understand the content of the work, to feel the events in the work with all their hearts, to perceive the work as an art of words, to be able to evaluate the behavior of the characters, to be able to draw independent conclusions from them and, having encountered such events, to prepare to edit. In this regard, in primary education it is necessary to approach the analysis of popular science and fiction works from a scientific point of view. To this end, theoretical and methodological training courses in literary analysis of popular science and fiction works, as well as "Children's Literature" should be organized in school education and it is advisable to include the subject "Theory of Literary Analysis". The subject "Methodology of Teaching Native Language in Primary Schools" methodically prepares students – future primary school teachers, therefore this question cannot be attributed to this subject.

Additionally, preparing 4th-grade pupils for reading literacy for the international PIRLS assessment based on the textbook "Book for Reading" and to help primary school teachers, the teaching aid "Literary Analysis in Reading Lessons in the 4th Grade" by Bakieva H. was created. This aid takes into account the pedagogical experience associated with this problem and its solution. In addition, methodological aids for teaching pupils reading literacy, i.e. analysis of popular science and fiction works, were recommended. They cannot be called sufficient [4; 56].

However, the international PIRLS requirements depend, first of all, on the literary, artistic, social, spiritual, educational level of the text recommended for reading and analysis. Textbooks should include works that encourage pupils to independent and creative thinking. The reader should feel that a good work creates various experiences in the reader (sadness, anxiety), encourages him to think, allows him to choose his own position. The tasks given on the text of the work should ensure the reading literacy of the pupils. In this regard, our textbooks also have shortcomings. Raising the reading literacy of pupils to a high level largely depends on teacher's knowledge of text analysis and pedagogical skills.

While describing the real situation in terms of checking the textbook texts, their interestingness, vitality, artistic perfection, as well as the content of the questions posed at the end of the text, then you can see texts that cannot stimulate pupils' emotions, cannot enrich their imagination and, on the contrary, extinguish their interests. For example, in the 3rd grade "Books for reading" based on the story "New House" by Kh.Murodov, 3rd graders are asked to carry sand, bricks and soil with them to the construction site, and they go to work on the construction site. After reading this story, the question "Does the work meet the requirements of the international standard?" arises.

Moreover, the tale of Guzalbegim "Sister of the River" in the 3rd paragraph, what does the proverb used in the tale mean, "Why did the sisters Syr Darya and Zarafshon have golden ears?", "Animals and plants go to school" (?) What is the "power of language" in the text "The Power of Language" (narrative)? Polat Momin's poem "Independence from Harmony" is made up of dry advice, it is impossible to find a basis that will convince and surprise the reader. In M. Gamidova's story "Knowledge of the Homeland" we see a very interesting life story from the author's perspective, but we do not see logic in the system of events, the plot is artificial.

Besides that, in the work "Homeland" is listed what is seen through the eyes of a child. Events do not encourage the student to think, do not develop artistic and aesthetic taste, do not develop the personality of the student. K. Turdiyeva poetically expresses what the reader sees in the poem "Around the Prosperous Neighborhood" [5;84]

The following paragraphs are no exception. The ambiguity of the content and logic has also affected its language.

In relation to the text of the work included in the textbook, questions should be asked aimed at a deep understanding of its content, independent research and creative thinking, connection with life, summing up, speech development.

In textbooks, little attention is paid to information related to the artistry of the work, the features of the language, the connection of plot events, characterization of characters, general conclusions. It is necessary to take into account that preparing pupils for international PIRLS tests of reading literacy is not just a one-time formal event, but an important place in the further plan of primary education.

It is known that in connection with reading works of art, the formation of artistic and aesthetic thinking of pupils in a personality-oriented education system aimed at self-awareness, the development of a sense of love for the Motherland, reading education, a special place is occupied by the study of children's literature as a work of art.

At present time primary school teachers need clearly substantiated, scientifically based instructions on reading methods. The methodology enables future primary school teachers to independently and consciously approach the content of literary education and its teaching, not only to study the experience of others, but also to consciously analyze the results of their activities and correctly focus on ensuring their ability to draw conclusions [1; 48].

The following didactic principles can be attributed to the basis of teaching methods in primary grades:

1. Education should have a comprehensive impact on pupils' understanding.
2. Pupils clearly understand the problem.
3. The teacher should be able to demonstrate new complex learning tasks in the context of familiar events, the ability to combine deduction with induction in the process of literary education [3; 177].

It is known to everyone that modern literary education is aimed at mastering those cultural resources that have been created and enriched throughout the history of mankind for centuries, preparing them for real life, making a conscious choice of profession, and teaching civilized behavior with the people around them.

Taking into consideration the above mentioned ideas it should be suggested the importance of clearly defining teaching methods, goals and objectives at each stage of literary education, taking into account the educational capabilities of pupils, where a deep understanding of the

features of a work of art as an artistic phenomenon, the application of existing literary knowledge and concepts to the analysis of planned works ensures the quality and effectiveness of reading lessons.

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